

Factors that facing rural development in South Sudan: a case study of Awerial county, lakes state

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Abstract

This study investigated factors that are hindering the development of rural areas to determine the existing approaches, policies, strategies, and potential resources, as well as examine the current socio-economic benefit of rural development to the local community and existing challenges to rural development. Propose possible interventions for rural people's integration in Awerial County. The study adopted quantitative and qualitative techniques to be reliable and accurate, and structured questionnaires were used to be easy to administer. The study population was the target demographic of 100 respondents. To select an 80-person sample population at random, the Krejcie and Morgan table from 1970 was used. But SPSS 16.0, a statistical package for social research, and Advance Excel were employed to analyze this study. Natural disasters such as floods and droughts harmed rural development by 42.5%; man-made disasters such as insecurity and conflict harmed rural development by 40%; insufficient access to capital harmed rural development by 37.5%; and the inaccessibility of necessities for livelihoods harmed rural development by 50%; the health sector was harmed by a shortage of skilled health personnel, as demonstrated by 32.5%. Furthermore, poverty affected rural development by 42.55%. The main limitations of this study are the language barrier among the respondents, limited access to information due to the Internet, and mobility. The practical implication of this study was to propose positive approaches, strategies, policies, and rural integrated modalities. On the basis of originality or value, the study presented new knowledge for public decision-making about rural development in South Sudan.

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Introduction

Empowerment in rural development, in particular, is critical in enabling households to engage in a mixed diversification strategy that combines staple crops with nonfarm activities and migration. This is a "last resort" technique for low-income households to secure food security and supplement an inadequate resource base. Controlling for activity choice, three empowerment characteristics, in particular confidence, group participation, and tenure security, have a large and favorable impact on income from staple and cash crops, which accounts for approximately 90% of household income on average. In fact, empowerment is the only human capital variable that has a strong and positive effect on total household income, opening up interesting avenues for policy interventions aimed at augmenting a household's cognitive ability, for example, through leadership training or encouraging producer group membership to increase rural poor incomes (Wouterse et al., 2014)

Background of the Study

There is no global agreement on what defines rural development, which is one of its primary issues. Rural development has been defined differently by many schools of thought. It is defined by DieJomah (1973) as a process of raising the standard of living of the rural population, as measured by food and nutrition, health, education, housing, recreation, and security. Adegboye (1973) defines it as the ongoing growth of rural people so that they can most effectively and efficiently use their intellect, technology, and other resources for the further development of both themselves and their resources. Uwakah (1985) sees it as a process of transitioning rural people from what is to what ought to be. According to the criteria above, the goal of rural development is the rural people, whom Olatunbosun (1973) referred to as Nigeria's neglected majority, Anthony (1981) referred to as the stagnating sector of the economy, and Ijere (1981) referred to as the other poverty-related qualities. According to Williams (1978), rural development encompasses a wide range of activities, including the creation of new jobs, more equitable access to arable land, equitable income distribution, widespread improvements in health, nutrition, and housing, the maintenance of law and order, and the creation of incentives and opportunities for saving, credit, and investment. It also entails expanding possibilities for individuals to reach their full potential via education and participation in decisions and actions that affect their life. After everything is said and done, the key point in the definition of rural development is enhancing the rural people's standard of living through their own efforts along with government help. In general, development aims to increase people's ability to control their own lives (Sen, 1999). According to (Stiglitz, 1999), development is considered as a societal revolution, a shift away from conventional ways of thinking and conventional means of production and toward more current patterns. In other words, advancement must improve people's lives in every way. In this context, (Serves, 1999) refers to multidimensional growth. The lack of rural development in South Sudan has exacerbated rural people's issues and has hastened the country's high pace of urbanization. In order to address rural issues, a number of statutory agencies have been established, as well as various rural development initiatives and rural-based research, which are supported by some ad hoc policies and plans. So far, rural development practice lacks a broad view of rural challenges. Under the current circumstances, many bodies are compelled to pursue contradictory policies. There are at least three fundamental issues with the various methods to rural development. The first is that there is little or no emphasis on rural development in national development plans. The second is the fragmentary nature approach and single-mindedness taken by rural executive agencies, which have frequently pursued a range of secular agriculture policies for reasons of establishment. Third, every endeavor to address rural issues tends to minimize the function of planning authorities. The necessity for a centralized body to coordinate and implement rural planning policies and programs (Tomori, 2010).

Problem Statement

Many groups and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) promote conservation agriculture and traditional farming methods as solutions to Sub-Saharan Africa's challenges of low agricultural output and soil degradation. The technical side of rural development may function in a laboratory setting on trial plots, but this does not imply that Conservation Agriculture works the same way in actuality. Because there is no one-size-fits-all approach for rural development, it is critical to integrate social and contextual variables as well. The following example shows conflicting uses for crop wastes. Mulching the soil with crop waste is an important rural development principle. Whereas smallholder farmers in Awerial County frequently have mixed crop animal farms, local authorities in South Sudan frequently lack the capacity to deliver public services. This particularly affects residents in rural areas, which account for 80% of the entire population. They do not have adequate access to safe drinking water, and the country lacks means for resolving or preventing land and livestock migration issues. Another concern is the scarcity of training facilities for local government officials. The rural population has little opportunities to voice their concerns to local government, participate in municipal decisions, and create their living environment. Furthermore, conflicts over water and land resources between farmers and cattle herders lead to violence in many places of South Sudan. As a result, vital crops are frequently unable to be harvested, and livestock herds are imperiled. This exacerbates current land conflicts and poses a new threat to food security. Therefore, the promotion of Conservation Agriculture should be tailored to local conditions. The way how rural development Conservation Agriculture is promoted affects adoption as well. As such, this study is aimed to investigate factors that are facing development of rural communities at Awerial County, in Lakes State of South Sudan there is a need in the adoption of Conservation Agriculture and improvement of traditional farming ways among smallholder farmers. First and foremost, the manner in which both projects advertise the techniques will be investigated, as promotion effects uptake. The efficiency of marketing as well as the spread of Rural Development will be addressed using the Adoption and Diffusion model of (Rogers, 1995).

Objectives of the Study

To investigate factors that are hindering development of rural areas at Awerial County of Lakes State in South Sudan, .to determine the existing approaches, policies and strategies and potential resources in Awerial County and the current utilization activities, to examine the current socio-economic benefits of rural development to local community and existing challenges to rural development and to propose possible interventions for rural people integration in Awerial County.

Research Questions of the study

What are the factors facing development of rural areas at Awerial County of Lakes State in South Sudan? What are the existing strategies and policies with regard to rural development in Awerial County? What are the economic and social benefits that the communities have gained from current rural development initiatives and what are the existing challenges facing rural development activities?How can community be integrated into rural development and land reform uses with in Awerial County?How does rural development enhance food security?

Justification

Development of Rural areas in South Sudan play the important roles as the South Sudan Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Cooperatives and Rural Development (MAFCRD) and the Ministry of Animal Resources and Fisheries (MARF) stated in the (Comprehensive Agricultural Development Master Plan ,2015) that the Comprehensive Agricultural Development Master

Plan (CAMP) was to guide agricultural development at the national and state levels in order to address hunger and food insecurity through the increase of food production; leverage the agricultural sector to improve rural livelihoods; generate income; diversify the economy through a modernized competitive; agricultural sector to harmonized and streamline public and private investments and development assistance in these sectors through enhanced capacity for planning and implementation. Thus, the finding of this study is expected to benefit the stakeholders of Rural development who will play a crucial role in raising the income of rural people; solving the unemployment problem of the countryside; checking rural urban migration; supporting and enhancing the effectiveness of agriculture; contributing social sector development especially health and education; and transforming the socio-economic environment of the countryside.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Globally, the neglect of rural industrialisation has exacerbated rural people's issues and has hastened the country's high pace of urbanization. A variety of governmental agencies, as well as various rural development programs and rural-based researches, have been developed to address rural issues, supported by certain ad hoc policies and growth plans. So far, rural industrialization practice has lacked a complete understanding of rural difficulties. Under the current circumstances, many bodies are compelled to pursue contradictory policies. In the many approaches to rural industrialisation, there are at least three key issue areas. The first is that rural industrialization receives little or no attention in national development programs. The second is the fragmented nature and single-minded attitude taken by agencies with executive responsibility in rural areas, which have frequently followed a set of secular agricultural policies for the sake of their institution. Third, every endeavor to address rural issues tends to underestimate the significance of planning authorities. The necessity to establish a centralized body to coordinate and implement rural planning policies and activities (Tomorl, 2010). Factors influencing rural productivity and lifestyle interact with one another, generating various types of rural development. As a result, the assessment indicator system of rural comprehensive development (RCD) was established to reveal the differentiation of rural development and identify the dominant factors affecting rural development, based on the main factors influencing rural development ability and long-term development potential. The principal component analysis and cluster analysis methods were used to separate the various sorts of factors influencing rural activity. The findings demonstrate that high-level rural development areas are primarily concentrated in the region's center, whereas low-level regions are primarily spread in the region's periphery, with considerable spatial difference characteristics. We split rural development into three categories and 11 zones, each with its own set of basic natural circumstances and external challenges. The categories indicate three probable outcomes of rural development: growth, decline, and extinction, as seen in industrialisation. Lin et al. (2019) According to (Gholamhossein Hosseininia and Hadi Fallahi, 2017), they argued on their findings that the major factors affecting rural entrepreneurship development in most African countries fall into 9 categories as individual, socio-cultural, infrastructural, natural and ecological, legal, educational, institutional, political, and economic. The interactive mechanism of the factors was in conformity with the grounded theory, and paradigm model under 3 theoretical components. The findings were true in a context of Awerial County remain dormant factors that affect entrepreneurship development as part of rural development.

Development: It is a necessary component of societies; in fact, any civilization that does not evolve is said to be stagnant. As a result, all societies are dynamic in some way. Many authors from various perspectives have described development as a term: (Abubakar,1981) views

qualitative development progress in all societies and all categories of people within cultures. Development, as defined by (Forest,1981), is the process of establishing the conditions for the realization of human identity. He stated that development must be characterized by a reduction in poverty, unemployment, and inequality, as well as a good level of nutrition, a high standard of health, a low infant mortality rate, and so on. Development, according to the aforementioned criteria, is essentially transforming the life of an individual, group of people, or community in terms of social amenities such as excellent health, good roads, adequate and clean water, education, and so on.

Conceptual Framework Figure. 1

Source: Primary Data 2022

The Key Factors facing Rural Community in South Sudan:

Rural Health: According to the American Hospital Association (2019), rural hospitals are the backbones of their communities, providing critical access to care for over 20% of Americans. They provide larger communal advantages in addition to their immediate impact on health and well-being. They are frequently the largest local employer and help recruit additional businesses, which helps promote economic stability. Having a hospital close demonstrates the vitality of the community. Despite the value they serve in communities across the country, many rural hospitals are struggling financially, and an alarming number of them have had to close their doors. 121 rural hospitals have closed since 2010, leaving rural Americans with fewer options and a longer travel time to receive treatment. Americans lose access to important services with each shutdown, and communities lose a key component of their local economies. Violence and epidemics, which erupt without notice but necessitate rapid action (Joy Lewis & Erik Rogan, 2019).

Poverty: In developing countries, one-third of the population is impoverished, particularly in rural communities. Individuals living in poverty include landless laborers and casual employees. Individuals that are expected to suffer negative consequences as a result of poverty include scheduled castes, scheduled tribes, families headed by women, the elderly, and children. Poverty in rural communities is defined by a lack of financial resources, land, assets, property, and other resources. Individuals struggle to sustain their livelihoods in an effective manner due to a lack of these resources (Chapter -2. Rural Poverty in India). As a result, poverty presents itself in a variety of overlapping and interconnected political, economic, and social factors. In the context of South Sudan, the incidence of poverty is quite high, and development in South Sudan remains among the lowest in the world, according to all metrics. Livelihoods are mostly subsistence-level, and economic development is slow. People are cut off from fundamental necessities since public services are virtually non-existent (Poverty Assessment South Sudan, Cesar et al., 2012).

Illiteracy: Illiteracy is defined as an individual's incapacity to identify, interpret, understand, produce, communicate, and compute utilizing printed and written resources in a variety of

contexts. In 1930, the United States Bureau of Census classified an illiterate as someone who is unable to read or write in any language. The idea of functional illiteracy was adopted by the 1940 census. Anyone with less than five years of education is considered functionally illiterate. Such people would also have difficulty participating in any activity in which adequate literacy skills are considered essential (Qamar, 2017).

Unemployment: Unemployment is defined as the state in which individuals are not engaged in any sort of labor, occupation, or task principally for the purpose of generating a source of revenue. The rural population has a severe unemployment problem as a result of significant hurdles to achieving better livelihood possibilities (Dr. Radhika Kapur, 2019).

Crime and Violence: Crime and violent crimes have been prevalent in rural villages. All persons, regardless of gender, age, caste, creed, color, religion, ethnicity, or socioeconomic status, have been victims of crime and violence, with poverty being the primary reason. On the other hand, more attention is paid to male children, specifically their education, health, diet and nutrition, participation in other activities, making important decisions, and so on. As a result, girls and women experience neglect and discrimination, and they are not given equal rights and opportunities as males (Dr. Radhika Kapur, 2019).

Approaches/Strategies for Rural Development in South Sudan:

Community Development: South Sudan produced the Agriculture Sector Policy Framework (ASPF) 2012-2017 in 2012, and 34 Community-Based Organizations (CBOs) were registered in five of the ten states. As part of the strategy to implement the Community Development Policy prepared in 2011, the government pledges to "empower communities and their leaders to successfully participate in conducting sustainable development activities with government support." This will entail reviving the Amadi Rural Development Institute and upgrading existing training curriculum to address certain new social and economic concerns confronting youngsters in rural and urban areas. This is intended to foster better living conditions for the entire community through active involvement and citizen initiative. It works primarily through the mobilization and inception of community self-help and cooperative initiatives, but with technical aid from government or voluntary agencies to improve rural circumstances.

Agricultural Extension Program: According to (MengistuDiress, 2010), the availability of arable land and a pleasant climate are both required, but not sufficient, conditions for the sector's successful development. The availability of logistics, especially crucial off-farm infrastructure, is a critical prerequisite for facilitating timely and cost-effective transfer of products to domestic and international markets. To compete effectively in regional and international markets, as well as against imports of agricultural products from neighboring countries, infrastructure such as feeder roads, airports with regular flights to market destinations, cold chain facilities such as cold storage at airports and other destinations, reliable road transport services at competitive freight rates, prompt customs clearance for exports and key agricultural inputs that must be imported are required. The research looks at how various households rely on different combinations of activities, the factors that influence each approach, and the implications for rural-urban links (Seraje, 2007).

Integrated Rural Development: The concept of Integrated Rural Development was popular among Western donors in the 1970s and garnered renewed interest in the 1990s. This concept efficiently incorporates numerous sectors and techniques, ranging from health care service provision, agricultural growth, education, and infrastructure enhancement to technical transfer, with local governments serving as counterparts to address the multifaceted causes of

poverty. The benefits of integrated rural development are defined as enabling multidisciplinary anti-poverty activities in rural areas, enabling solutions to regional problems, targeting underprivileged populations, and encouraging local people, local administrative institutions, and civil society participation (Effective Approaches for Rural Development, Chapter 4, p. 207).

Co-ordinate Rural Development: This is consistent with integrated rural development. In line with this, the University of Life launched a rural development project, the University of Nigeria Nsukka (UNN) established a pilot project 6 kilometers from campus, and the Asian Broadcasting Union (ABU) Zaria established AERLS (Agriculture Extension research liaison services). Home Economists, Geographers, Agriculture, Economists, Extensions, Animal, Crop, and Soil Scientists, for example, all collaborate on the Okpuje Project at UNN. The weather forecast is handled by the geographer, and the farmer show is taught by the extensions. Agricultural economists design policies that lead to the resolution of farmers' difficulties, while soil scientists test the soil. South Sudan's Agriculture Sector Policy Framework has backed this up (ASPF 2012-2017).

Human Capabilities: When the improvement of human capabilities is considered, the emphasis is placed on one's health and educational levels. Individuals' health status is seen as deplorable in rural settings. Individuals who are suffering from health issues or illnesses will almost surely have difficulty participating in any chores or activities. As a result, individuals notice a decrease in productivity. As a result, expanding medical and health care facilities is critical for South Sudan's rural development (Dr. Radhika Kapur, 2019).

Problems of rural Development in Awerial County under Poverty

Occurrence of Natural Calamities and Disasters: Geographically, Awerial County is located along the Nile River and other seasonal rivers, which frequently leads to the occurrence of natural calamities and disasters such as floods and droughts, among others, which are highly destructive to the livelihoods of the rural community. This would result in enormous loss of life, wealth, and property, leading to] causes of poverty (Kapur,2019).

Inadequate Financial Support: Despite the fact that South Sudan became an officially independent country on July 9, 2011, the majority of rural people in Awerial County are still illiterate and unaware, and lack the ability to manage finances and save effectively, which leads to a reduction in the prevalence of poverty in the area. As more rural communities in Awerial County lack full livelihood skills, it hurts their social and economic standing in particular, while also slowing the country's economic growth as a result of political progress aggravated by a new civil conflict that began in late 2013. Despite the fact that a regionally supported peace accord was signed in mid-2015, it effectively failed and combat restarted in 2016 to 2018, and it appears set to continue for the foreseeable future. As a result, hundreds of thousands of people have been displaced across the country, and Awerial county has become the epicenter of a major humanitarian crisis, forcing the host community of Awerial to choose between continuing their ancestors' farming lifestyle or starting a new modern business due to the presence of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in the area. Because there is no visible and quick route out of the current cycle of violence, poverty is prevalent in the Awerial community in rural areas (ICED,2018).

Large Families size: It is the conventions and cultural beliefs that cause individuals to have big families, and one nuclear family is normally anticipated to have more than two children, as well as the fundamental home structure in the context of Awerial, that cause poverty. South Sudanese in other nations may wish to have smaller families. Unless uncontrolled circumstances impede this arrangement, the extended family usually lives with the nuclear

family. As a result of South Sudan's decades of conflict, many people have been orphaned or widowed, and they are usually taken in and cared for by extended family networks. Based on this scenario, the average South Sudanese household usually consists of three generations: (1) the eldest couple, (2) their sons, sons' wives, and any unmarried daughters, and (3) their grandchildren, resulting in poverty in rural areas in South Sudan (<https://culturalatlas.sbs>).

Child Labor: Child labor has persisted in developing countries. Individuals from disadvantaged, marginalized, and socioeconomically backward areas of society are more likely to encourage their children to engage in various forms of labor practices, so depriving them of an education. Children are even working in hazardous industries such as shoe polishing, gem cutting, bed rolling, plantations, agriculture, and lock business enterprises. It is critical for them to have suitable knowledge and training in these areas in order to carry out their job tasks properly. Because the youngsters are frequently employed full-time in these enterprises and households, they are unable to polish their literacy abilities (Dr. Radhika Kapur, 2019). In comparison to the situation in Awerial County, Child Labor had been practiced in the form of gender division of labor based on biological sex among the children, with girls always becoming the victims of this social problem in the societies, which needs to be solved by implementing the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW). Failure to do so may compound the county's future and result in poor enrollment of females in schools in Awerial, resulting in the greatest level of illiteracy among common inhabitants (Girls' Education Strategy for South Sudan 2015 - 2017, p. 8).

Skills Mismatch: Individuals must possess the necessary abilities in accordance with the job criteria. For example, if a person works as a carpenter, he must have sufficient understanding of his trade and so on. When individuals have skills that are incompatible with job needs, they have difficulty finding work (Dr Radhika Kapur,2019). Mismatches in skill sets are one of the most crucial aspects of the private sector for policymakers to identify. One of the most elusive tasks of labor economics is determining what skills job seekers already have and whether or not those skills are sufficient for the roles available. South Sudanese society must first define which talents are most vital for firm owners to consider when keeping present personnel in order to detect skill set mismatches. When these skills are assumed to be the primary skills required by employers since they serve as the criterion by which employees differentiate themselves. As a result, if a company decides to keep an employee, the appraisal of their talents and performance is compared to other workers of similar standing, assuming everything else is equal, because these people already went through a screening procedure at the hiring stage. As a result, it can be claimed that skill mismatch among Awerial's rural residents is one of the major reasons of unemployment, particularly among the poor, marginalized, and socioeconomically backward elements of society (Report No. -SS. World Bank Group,2014).

Social Restraints upon Women: As previously noted, social constraints are put on women in rural communities. They are regarded as less than men and are denied equal rights and opportunities. The prevalence of discriminatory treatment towards women is a hindrance not just to acquiring literacy, but also to obtaining work possibilities. They are forced to remain in their homes and carry out household tasks. Other social constraints put on individuals include a lack of participation in decision-making processes, as well as social, cultural, political, economic, and religious functions, among others (Radhika, 2019).

Strategies and policies adopted with regard to rural development in Awerial County: The key rural development methods and policies implemented in Awerial County included, but were not limited to, endogenous and participatory development, target group strategy, integrated or holistic strategy, and other local techniques that can aid in rural development.

Social and economic benefits as a result of policies and strategies of rural development Livelihoods diversification and technology transfer: Prior to the implementation of rural development policies and strategies in 2010, the rural community of Awerial county relied heavily on cattle rearing, crop production, and fishing, undermining other activities such as collecting wild food, hunting, and trade that provided supplementary sources of food. Awerial County's rural development policies and methods reduced poor fishing access by providing appropriate fishing gear and eliminating significant post-harvest losses. Despite Awerial County's abundant water resources, there is still minimal small-scale irrigation during the dry season, but current policies and tactics can support traditional hand irrigation in riverbeds for tobacco and local vegetable crops during the dry season. Rural development plans and initiatives for Awerial county, in partnership with humanitarian organizations, had eradicated such attitudes to lessen considerable import from surrounding counties in order to alleviate the rural community's prolonged food insecurity (Emergency response and rehabilitation for food and agriculture August 2010).

Conservation of agriculture: Conservation agriculture (CA) seeks to produce sustainable and profitable agriculture, and hence enhance farmers' livelihoods, by implementing three principles: minimal soil disturbance, permanent soil cover, and crop rotations. Conservation agriculture has been shown to function in a range of agro-ecological zones and farming systems by combining economic agricultural output with environmental concerns and sustainability. Because of its potential, rural development policies and strategies in Awerial county support FAO in promoting CA, which integrates different areas of technical expertise and aims to facilitate its implementation throughout the county as it impacts a number of aspects related to agricultural production decline. For example, in 2009, FAO presented CA to reduce the environmental impact of conventional plowing using the moldboard plough, and the Awerial County Department of Agriculture advocated good techniques and policies to maintain soil fertility in rural areas for Awerial County (Plan of Action for Southern Sudan, 2010).

Promotion of animal traction production: Animal traction in Southern Sudan has been promoted by the rural community to boost output in Awerial County since the early 1970s. This is the result of rural development policies and strategies in Awerial County. According to the Plan of Action for Southern Sudan (2010), FAO and the County Agriculture Department are pushing animal traction as the best technology for expanding agricultural land. Awerial County has a proportion of homes who employ animal traction, particularly in Awerial North (Bunagok; Alel; AbuyungPayams). According to rural development policies and strategies in Awerial County, through animal traction, the area under cultivation per household can be increased by 4 to 8 feddans (a 100 to 400 percent increase compared to the use of hand tools), potentially resulting in increased food production to meet household food needs and generate income through marketing surplus (Plan of Action for Southern Sudan, 2010).

Integrated Rural development in Awerial County can be explained by Environmental Conditions: Individuals must develop the skills and abilities necessary to make efficient use of the resources provided by natural environmental conditions. Individuals, on the other hand, are expected to raise awareness about the numerous tactics and approaches required for environmental preservation. Controlling various types of pollution is viewed as critical.

Individuals in rural areas must be aware of numerous tactics and approaches for keeping water bodies and environmental conditions clean. Awerial County has practiced integrated environmental conditions to ensure that resources are used effectively to improve the living conditions and rural population on seven (7) cross-cutting issues that have been identified as important, which include environment, gender equality, youth employment, capacity-building, human rights, HIV/AIDS, and corruption. These challenges are addressed throughout SSDP, and cross-cutting issues are intrinsic to the programs in some cases (South Sudan Development Plan) (2011 – 2013, p. 20).

Infrastructure: Infrastructure development is critical to the development of rural communities. Roads, transportation, communications, power supplies, water supplies, public services, broadcasting, and telecommunications are among the infrastructure facilities that must be created in remote towns. Individuals in rural household's face power and water supply shortages. They are necessary to get water from neighboring wells or sources of water. The conditions of roads and forms of transportation are not in a well-developed state, causing difficulties for folks transferring from one location to another. As a result, investments in infrastructure are critical to rural development (Kapur,2019).

Rural Development and self-reliance in Awerial County

Food Production: In Awerial County, there are examples of project implementation in terms of food development. In order to alleviate the problem of hunger and improve food availability in South Sudan, a comprehensive approach must be implemented. The establishment of a mechanism for transmitting lessons to other rural areas, as well as the development of agricultural techniques, must be carried out. It is obvious that initiatives to boost agricultural output should be implemented to supplement food production. Using current and new methodologies, scientific approaches, and technologies is one of the most important ways to boost agricultural output. Farmers and agricultural laborers are enrolled in training centers and pursue educational programs, which may raise their awareness in these areas. Furthermore, a method for transmitting lessons learnt from model initiatives to other areas should be established. To attain the intended results, production plans and agricultural development plans should work together. The importance of agriculture in driving growth and reducing rural poverty and malnutrition has been stressed in the (World Development Report, 2008)

Reconstruction Support: The term "reconstruction" refers to the building of dwellings, shelters, schools, training facilities, hospitals, medical centers, market areas, and other public locations. In the context of South Sudan and Awerial County, which have experienced the longest civil wars, from 1955 to 2005 and again from 2013 to date, it is necessary for rural residents to re-start their lives after conflicts or large disasters, with priority given to the reconstruction of rural areas, where a large portion of these citizens live. When a comprehensive approach involving aid in agriculture, industry, education, health, and infrastructure sectors is required for post-conflict rural reconstruction. This results in effective growth and development of individuals, communities, and public spaces such as parks, playgrounds, theaters, and religious facilities, among others. Apart from the creation of these sites, it is necessary to ensure that in rural communities, enough infrastructure and civic amenities are established. Policies must be developed so that homes do not face water and electricity shortages. Water, power, and lighting facilities within households are seen as critical, allowing persons to carry out their jobs and maintain their living conditions in an effective manner (Effective Approach for Rural Development, Chapter, pg -205).

Empirical Studies

Empirical Study I: According to Jomehpour's (2017) article titled "Identifying Strategic Priorities for the Sustainable Development of Rural Areas Based on Local Community Planning." He claimed that the only way to achieve sustainable development of rural areas and local communities is to establish a governance system based on local community planning, as they are the primary beneficiaries of development projects. He also demonstrated that without addressing the position of impoverished and destitute rural society, any development strategy could face major difficulties in achieving its goals. According to the summary and conclusions of this Journal, one of the techniques for improving the quality of life in rural regions and closing the gap between urban and rural society is to truly understand them and contribute to local planning. That is, any strategic plan for the sustainable development of rural societies entails a comprehensive strategy and integrated attitude toward rural development as a component of the national territory's social, economic, geographical, and political systems (Jomehpour, 2017).

Empirical Study II: According to Leslie et al. (2017) in their article titled "How land reform and rural development might help reduce poverty in South Africa," in their summary and conclusions, a variety of various methods, such as the construction of informal land markets, could be employed in different regions. This suggests that underutilized rural land is worth a lot of money. However, this value is being eroded by a lack of suitable titling options and land management systems. A unified and comprehensive land reform policy is required (Leslie and TimGB, 2017).

Research Methodology

The research could be exploratory, descriptive, explanatory, evaluative, or a combination of these. Exploratory research is defined as "research that seeks fresh insights into phenomena, asks questions, and evaluates phenomena in a new light." Descriptive research is defined as "research with the goal of producing an accurate portrayal of people, events, or situations." Explanatory research is defined as "research focused on investigating a scenario or an issue in order to explain the relationships between variables." While the goal of evaluative research is to "to determine how well something works" (Saunders, 2011). This study is classified as descriptive research because its goal is to evaluate the variables that impede rural development in South Sudan and to investigate the correlations that exist between factors that impede rural development and rural development in South Sudan. As a result, the analytical descriptive technique will be used in this study. A questionnaire will be utilized to gather data and assess factors for the research, and it will be given to respondents from the field of study in Awerial. SPSS software will be used to analyze the results. The method used to conduct a scientific investigation is known as research design (both, 2005). It is the researcher's study plan in which he describes the type of scientific investigation he intends to conduct. This study used a survey research design. The survey research approach entails selecting a small sample of the overall population for data collection and analysis using a sampling strategy (Robson, 2002). A approach for conducting research that incorporates an analysis of a specific current event inside its real-life setting using various sources of verification, which advances data validation. Key and secondary data sources were the primary sources of information.

PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF FINDING

This section is concerned with data presentation, discussion of findings, analysis, and interpretations of data obtained from raw. Out of 100 structured questionnaires issued to respondents in the field, all 80 were successfully returned and selected for data analysis. For this study, the tabulation form of data presentation, graphs, and pie chart were important, as

well as the statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS 16.0) and advanced Microsoft Excel to obtain the following Tables.

Table 1: Gender of Respondents

Gender of Respondents	Frequency	Valid Percent
Male	43	53.8
Female	37	46.3
Total	80	100.0

Source: Researcher Primary Data 2022

According to the analytical results in table 1, 34 respondents were male and earned 53.8%, while 37 respondents were female and earned 46.3%. This implied that the majority of the personnel who served in Awerial County were male, implying that gender equality was required.

Figure 1: Pie Chart Showing Gender of Respondents

Table 2: Age Range of Respondents

Age Range of the Respondents	Frequency	Valid Percent
16-25 Years	15	18.8
26-35 Years	40	50.0
36-45 Years	13	16.3
46-55 Years	8	10.0
56 – above Years	4	5.0
Total	80	100.0

Source: Researcher Primary Data 2022

The study results showed that the age range of 16-25 years had 15 respondents with 18.8%, the age range of 26-35 years had 40 respondents with 50.0%, the age range of 36-45 years has 13 respondents with 16.3%, and the age range of 46-55 years had 8 respondents with 10.0%. 4.0% of respondents are over the age of 56, implying that the majority of respondents are between the ages of 26 and 35.

Figure 2: Bar Graph showing Age Range of Respondents

Table 3. Marital Status of Respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Valid Percent
Single	20	25.0
Married	50	62.5
Divorced	1	1.25
Separated	1	1.25
Widower/Widow	8	10.0
Total	80	100.0

Source: Researcher Primary Data 2022

According to the results of the marital status analysis, 20 respondents were single (25.0%), 50 respondents were married (62.5%), 1 respondent divorced with his couple (1.25%), and 1 respondent also separated with his couple (1.25%). As a result, the majority of respondents to whom questionnaires were distributed were married.

Figure 3: Bar Graph showing Marital Status of Respondents

Table 4: Showing Education Qualification of Respondents

Level of Education of Respondents	Frequency	Valid Percent
Primary Level	10	12.5
Secondary Level	30	37.5
College Level	13	16.3
University Level	24	30.0
Master's Degree/PhD Level	3	3.8
Total	80	100.0

Source: Researcher Primary Data 2022

Analysis of respondents' educational levels reveals that 10 were Primary Level with 12.5%, 30 were Secondary Level with 37.5%, 13 were College Level with 16.3%, 24 were University Level with 30.0%, and 3 were Master's Degree/PhD level with 3.8%. That means that the majority of the employees serving in Awerial County are at the University Level.

Table 5: Showing Occupation status of Respondents

Occupation Status of Respondents	Frequency	Valid Percent
Self-Employed	6	7.5
Government Employee	40	50.0
Private Employee	20	25.0
Unemployed	14	17.5
Total	80	100.0

Source: Researcher Primary Data 2022

According to the analysis results in table 5 above, employees who were self-employed were 6 respondents earning 7.5%, government employees serving within Awerial county were 40 respondents earning 50.0%, respondents serving in the private sector were 20 respondents earning 25.0%, and 14 respondents were unemployed earning 17.5%. That suggests that the majority of the questionnaires were completed by government employees serving in Awerial County.

Graph Showing occupation status of Respondents

Factors facing Rural Development in South Sudan

Table 6: Showing factors facing Rural Development in South Sudan

Likert Rating points	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Not Sure		Agree		Strongly Agree	
	F	P (%)	F	P (%)	F	P (%)	F	P (%)	F	P (%)
Factors Facing rural Development at Awerial County of Lake State										
Natural disasters (e.g. flood, drought)	4	9.1	7	15.9	8	18.2	34	42.5	19	43.2
Man-made disasters (e.g. insecurity, conflict)	5	11.4	11	25.0	13	29.5	32	40.0	30	37.5
Inadequate access capital	7	15.9	4	9.1	13	29.5	26	32.5	30	37.5
Fewer educational institutions	4	9.1	3	3.75	11	25.0	32	40.0	30	37.5
Frequent displacement	12	15.0	9	11.3	15	18.8	29	36.3	15	18.8
Inadequate of Rural Broadband might be on of challenge that facing rural development at Awerial County of Lakes Stat in South Sudan										
Lack of online education	9	11.3	8	10.0	18	22.5	22	27.5	23	28.8
Lack of internet connectivity	2	2.5	8	10.0	13	16.3	27	33.8	30	37.5
Inadequate of construction materials	2	2.5	10	12.5	11	13.8	33	28.8	24	30.0
Inaccessible the necessity needs for livelihoods	5	6.3	6	7.5	12	15.0	40	50.0	17	21.3
Poor roads	7	8.8	4	5.0	11	13.8	19	23.8	39	48.8
The factors that facing rural development at Awerial County in relation to Rural heath										
Workforce shortage	6	7.5	16	20.0	16	20.0	26	32.5	16	30.0
Geographic isolation	8	10.0	16	20.0	20	25.0	23	28.8	13	16.3
Underfunding primary Care in rural	2	2.5	6	7.5	9	11.3	33	41.3	30	37.5
Rural primary lack of basic elements of infrastructure (e.g. water, electricity)	4	5.0	5	6.3	10	12.5	25	31.5	36	45.0
Epidemic disease occurs with little warning	8	10.0	9	11.3	16	20.0	30	37.5	17	21.3
Factors facing rural development in relation to prevalent poverty at Awerial County										
Inadequate Financial Management:	4	5.0	5	6.3	10	12.5	35	43.5	26	32.5
Illiteracy and Unawareness:	4	5.0	11	13.8	21	26.3	27	33.8	17	21.3
Large Families	4	5.0	11	13.8	13	16.3	32	40.0	20	25.0
Rural- urban Migration	7	8.8	9	11.3	15	18.8	29	36.3	20	25.0
Participation in Minority Jobs										
Factors facing rural development in relation to illiteracy of rural individuals at Awerial County										
Lack of Financial Resources:	4	5.0	7	8.8	9	11.3	35	43.8	25	31.3
Parental Illiteracy	2	2.5	5	6.3	12	15.0	30	37.5	31	38.8
Lack of Educational Facilities	5	6.3	5	6.3	7	8.8	24	30.0	31	38.8
Lack of Teaching-Learning Methods	3	3.8	8	10.0	5	6.3	7	8.8	39	48.8
Transportation Problems	2	2.5	8	10.0	15	18.8	15	18.8	30	37.5
Factors facing rural development at Awerial County of Lakes in relation to Unemployment										
Increased Education Expectations	10	12.5	10	12.5	14	17.5	29	36.3	17	21.3
Lack of Basic Literacy Skills:	7	8.8	8	10.0	7	8.8	28	35.0	30	37.5
Temporary Contracts	5	6.3	7	8.8	15	18.8	30	37.5	23	28.8
Skills Mismatch	3	3.8	5	6.3	18	22.5	30	37.5	24	30.0
Lack of Training for Work	3	3.75	11	13.8	12	15.0	36	45.0	18	22.5
Factors facing rural development at Awerial County of Lakes State in relation to rampant Crime & violence in among rural individuals										
Physical Abuse	8	10.0	18	22.5	12	15.0	28	35.0	14	17.5
Exploitation	14	17.5	10	12.5	13	16.3	27	33.8	16	20.0
Theft and Robbery	10	12.5	10	12.5	12	15.0	22	27.5	26	32.5
Domestic Violence	4	5.0	8	10.0	13	16.3	37	46.3	18	22.5
Dowry Deaths	8	10.0	14	17.5	17	21.3	24	30.0	17	21.3

Source: Researcher Field Primary Data 2022

In the above table, the results on factors affecting rural development in Awerial County demonstrate that natural disasters such as flood and drought contribute negatively to rural development by 43.2%, while man-made disasters such as insecurity and conflict contribute negatively by 40.0%. Inadequate access capital was cited by 32.5% of respondents as a barrier to rural development in Awerial County. 37.5% indicate that fewer educational institutions were a factor influencing rural development, while 36.3% indicate that frequent displacement of people was a factor that contributed negatively to rural development in Awerial County.

Awerial County's rural development was hampered by a 33.8% absence of internet connectivity. According to 41.3% of respondents, insufficient construction materials hampered rural development in Awerial County. Concerning the inaccessibility of necessary needs for livelihood, 50.0% indicates that inaccessibility of necessity needs for livelihood affected rural development, while 48.8% indicates that bad road network affected rural development activities in Awerial County. In terms of labor force in rural health, A personnel shortfall in the health sector in Awerial County has hampered rural development by 20.0%. Furthermore, Awerial County is geographically isolated. Geographic isolation impacted negatively to rural development efforts in the County by 28.8%. In terms of primary health care underfunding in Awerial County, 37.5% indicates that underfunding has an impact on primary health care activities in Awerial County. Rural growth was hampered by 45.0% due to a lack of fundamental factors such as infrastructure (clean water and electricity). 37.5% indicates that epidemic disease occurs within Awerial County with little warning, affecting rural development in the county. Furthermore, in terms of factors connected with the prevalence of poverty in terms of insufficient financial management, rural development was damaged by 42.5% in terms of illiteracy and unwariness. Illiteracy and ignorance contributed to poor rural development in Awerial County by 43.8%. Large family size also had a 33.8% impact on rural development, with 40.0% indicating that rural urban migration was one of the variables influencing rural development. Lack of involvement in minority jobs hampered rural growth by 25.0% due to a lack of financial resources, and parental illiteracy in Awerial county contributed to low rural development, as shown. Lack of schooling facilities has hampered rural development growth in Awerial County by 38.8%. The lack of teaching learning methods in the education sector was a factor affecting rural development in terms of realizing quality education by 42.5%. On transportation as a factor affecting rural development, 37.5% of respondents indicated that transportation was a factor affecting rural development. The analysis results in respect to factors affecting rural development in terms of rural unemployment were described below. Increased education expectations hampered rural development in Awerial County by 36.3%, lack of basic literacy skills hampered rural development by 37.5%, and skill mismatch hampered rural development activities by 37.5% in Awerial County.

Lack of training on rural development work hampered rural development progress by 45.0%, with 35.0% indicating that physical abuse was a kind of crime and violence related with the decline of rural development in Awerial County. Concerning rampant crime and violence in the form of exploitation, 33.8% indicate that exploitation is a kind of crime and violence that affects rural development in South Sudan, particularly in Awerial County. 27.5% indicate that theft and robbery are forms of crime and violence that have an impact on rural development operations in Awerial County, South Sudan, in terms of domestic violence. Domestic violence was a kind of crime and violence that affected rural development in one way or another in Awerial County, with 46.3% indicating that dowry death was a form of crime and violence. Dowry death is a form of crime and violence that has a negative impact on rural development in Awerial County, according to 30.0% of respondents.

Determination of the existing approaches, policies, strategies and potential resources in Awerial County and the current utilization activities

Table 7: Showing Determination of the existing approaches, policies, strategies and potential resources in Awerial County and the current utilization activities

Likert Rating points	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Not Sure		Agree		Strongly Agree	
	F	P (%)	F	P (%)	F	P (%)	F	P (%)	F	P (%)
The approaches for rural development at Awerial County of Lakes State in South Sudan can include:										
Community Development	2	4.5	4	9.1	11	13.8	40	50.0	23	28.8
Agricultural Extension Program	1	1.3	2	2.5	6	7.5	40	50.0	31	38.8
Integrated Rural Development:	2	2.5	2	2.5	13	16.3	38	47.5	25	31.3
Co-ordinate Rural Development	2	2.5	7	8.8	14	17.5	41	51.3	16	20.0
Economic Capabilities	4	5.0	4	5.0	14	17.5	36	45.0	22	27.5
The strategies for rural development at Awerial County of Lakes State in South Sudan comprise of:										
Area development strategy	2	2.5	10	12.5	14	17.5	38	47.5	16	20.0
Integrated Strategy	3	3.8	7	8.8	12	15.0	35	43.8	23	28.8
Participatory Strategy	1	1.3	4	5.0	13	16.3	32	40.0	30	37.5
Food Production:	2	2.5	4	5.0	8	10.0	38	47.8	28	35.0
Administrative Capabilities	1	1.3	7	8.8	14	17.5	32	40.0	26	32.5
The policies for rural development at Awerial County of Lakes State in South Sudan might correspond to South Sudan policies about rural areas										
Education	4	5.0	6	7.5	5	6.3	29	36.3	36	45.0
Technology	7	8.8	10	12.5	14	17.5	30	37.5	19	23.8
Training Programs	3	3.8	5	6.3	10	12.5	39	48.8	23	28.8
Self-Reliance	2	2.5	7	8.8	15	18.8	30	37.5	26	32.5
Law and Order	3	3.8	4	5.0	11	13.8	30	37.5	32	40.0

Source: *Researcher Field Primary Data 2022*

Analysis of existing approaches, policies, strategies, potential resources, and current resources in Awerial County revealed that community development was one of the approaches prioritized by rural areas in the County, and agriculture extension program was also a strategy associated with rural development. Furthermore, 47.5% of respondents felt that integrated rural development was a strategy and technique for rural development. 51.3% indicate that rural development coordination was the County's strategy and approach to rural development operations. In terms of economic capabilities for rural development, 45.0% of respondents in Awerial County answered that economic capabilities were a strategy for rural development. However, 47.5% of Awerial County's rural development initiatives included an area development strategy. One of the proposals for rural development in Awerial County, according to 43.8%, was an intergraded strategy. 40.0% of rural authorities' plans for rural development include a participatory strategy, while 47.5% do not. Food production strategy was one of the techniques implemented to reduce food insecurity in the county. Administrative capacities in terms of training local people were mentioned by 54.5% of respondents as part of Awerial County's rural development strategy. On rural authorities' initiatives for rural development in Awerial County. 45.0% indicate that education was one of the policies established for rural development in Awerial County, while 37.5% indicate that technology was one of the policies established for enhancing rural development in Awerial County. And 37.5% demonstrates that self-sufficiency among local people remains a feasible rural development policy. 40.0% indicated that law and order was a rural development policy.

The current socio-economic benefits of rural development to local community and existing challenges to rural development at Awerial County of Lakes State in South Sudan. Table 8 showing current socio-economic benefits of rural development to local community and existing challenges to rural development at Awerial County of Lakes State in South Sudan

Table 8: current socio-economic benefits of rural development to local community and existing challenges to rural development at Awerial County of Lakes State in South Sudan

Likert Rating points	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Not Sure		Agree		Strongly Agree	
	F	P (%)	F	P (%)	F	P (%)	F	P (%)	F	P (%)
Statements										
The current socio-economic benefit of rural development to local community at Awerial County of Lakes State in South Sudan can include										
Endogenous development:	2	4.5	8	10.0	24	30.0	35	43.8	11	13.8
Participatory development	2	4.5	6	7.5	11	25.0	41	51.3	20	25.0
Human capabilities:	2	4.5	6	7.5	11	25.0	40	50.0	21	26.3
Protective capabilities	4	5.0	5	6.3	9	11.3	46	57.5	16	20.0
Political capabilities	2	4.5	4	5.0	19	23.8	36	45.0	19	23.8
The existing challenges to rural development at Awerial County of Lakes State in South Sudan might include:										
Lack of Interest in Studies	2	2.5	9	11.3	13	16.3	29	36.3	27	33.8
Child Labour	3	3.8	13	16.8	14	17.5	29	36.3	21	26.3
Social Restraints upon Women	2	2.5	4	5.0	13	16.8	35	43.8	26	32.5
Health Problems and Illnesses	3	3.8	6	7.5	8	10.0	32	40.0	31	38.8
Sexual Harassment	13	16.3	15	18.8	14	17.5	21	26.3	17	21.3

Source: Researcher Field Primary Data 2022

The present socio-economic advantage of rural development to the local community in Awerial County was 43.8%, indicating that endogenous development was connected with the County's current socio-economic benefit for rural development. In terms of local people participation in the project, 51.3% indicated that participatory development was not related with rural development. Human capabilities were among the current social economic for community development in Awerial at 50.0%. Awerial County's rural development included protective development in 57.5% of cases. On the obstacles facing rural development, 43.8% say a lack of formal schooling has hampered growth, and 36.3% say child labor is one of the issues confronting rural development in the county. On social constraints on women, 43.8% disclose that women in Awerial County have encountered various forms of abuse, making them vulnerable. 40.0% indicates that health issues and illness continue to be a barrier to rural development in Awerial County. Furthermore, 26.3% reported that 3 respondents disagreed with the assertion made by 3.8% that health problems and illness were not a barrier to rural development. As shown by 7.5%, 6 people disagree with the statement. 8 respondents were unsure about the subject, with 10.0% unsure whether health problems and illness were among the challenges facing rural development. 32 respondents agreed with the statement, with 40.0% indicating that health problems and illness were among the challenges facing rural development, and 26.3% indicating that health problems and illness were challenges facing rural development in Awerial County. And 26.3% said one of the difficulties to rural development in Awerial County was sexual harassment among rural women and girls.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the establishment of a rural area strategy was critical for local people in South Sudan to have access to essential services; nevertheless, this study demonstrates that rural development within Awerial County was hampered by a variety of problems. In the above table, the results on factors affecting rural development in Awerial County demonstrate that natural disasters such as flood and drought contribute negatively to rural development by 43.2%, while man-made disasters such as insecurity and conflict contribute negatively by 40.0%. Inadequate access capital was cited by 32.5% of respondents as a barrier to rural development in Awerial County. 37.5% indicate that fewer educational institutions were a factor influencing rural development, while 36.3% indicate that frequent displacement of people was a factor that contributed negatively to rural development in Awerial County. Awerial County's rural

development was hampered by a 33.8% absence of internet connectivity. According to 41.3% of respondents, insufficient construction materials hampered rural development in Awerial County. Concerning inaccessibility of necessary needs for livelihood, 50.0% indicates that inaccessibility of necessity needs for livelihood hampered rural development, while 48.8% indicates that a poor road network hampered rural development activities in Awerial County. In terms of workforce, a workforce shortage of 20.0% in the health sector in Awerial County has hampered rural development. Furthermore, Awerial County is geographically isolated. Geographic isolation impacted negatively to rural development efforts in the County by 28.8%. In terms of primary health care underfunding in Awerial County, 37.5% indicates that underfunding has an impact on primary health care activities in Awerial County. Rural growth was hampered by 45.0% due to a lack of fundamental factors such as infrastructure (clean water and electricity). 37.5% indicates that epidemic disease occurs within Awerial County with little warning, affecting rural development in the county. Furthermore, in terms of factors connected with the prevalence of poverty in terms of insufficient financial management, rural development was damaged by 42.5% in terms of illiteracy and unwariness. Illiteracy and ignorance contributed to poor rural development in Awerial County by 43.8%. Large family size also had a 33.8% impact on rural development, with 40.0% indicating that rural urban migration was one of the variables influencing rural development. Parental illiteracy in Awerial County contributed to poor rural development as shown by 38.8% lack of education facilities has affected rural development progress by 48.8% in Awerial County by 48.8% lack of teaching learning method in education sector was a factor affecting rural development in terms of realizing quality. Transportation was cited as a factor influencing rural development by 37.5% of respondents. The study reveals that there are several major factors associated with the decline of rural development in Awerial County, including natural disasters such as floods and droughts, man-made disasters such as insecurity and conflict, insufficient access to capital, poor infrastructures, and poor roads. On the other hand, improving policies, strategies, and approaches was the only way forward for rural development success.

Recommendations

The study suggested the following potential interventions with a focus on improving rural development approaches, policies, and strategies that can embrace rural development in Awerial County.

Approaches: Improvement of rural local administrative units' economic capacities; Strategies for community development should be promoted. Agricultural extension program and integrated rural development promotion Stabilized economic, social, cultural, and environmental well-being and policies; Improve feeder roads in collaboration with the county; Formation of a village serving loan association to assist rural development in the county; Raising awareness about the bad attitudes caused by domestic violence; Within Awerial County, advocate for environmental degradation.

Policies: To develop training programs for local administrators in Awerial County; To provide free education to the local community in the County; To increase security and law enforcement activities in Awerial County; To improve and expand health services in Awerial County; to educate the population about human rights; and to address customary law, social and traditional harm in order to protect the local community. To create policies that eliminate all sorts of development illiteracy inside Awerial County; To begin income generation in rural areas in order to eliminate poverty and hunger by providing essential services to rural inhabitants.

Strategies: Provision of food inside Awerial County through empowering the agriculture sector; enhancement of administrative capacities for local administrators within Awerial County; improvement of domestic business, education system, and good marketing system;

Encouragement of community involvement and empowerment of the private sector via a bottom-up approach to establish acceptable strategies to guide rural development.

REFERENCES

- Zadawa, A.N., Omran, A. (2020). Rural Development in Africa: Challenges and Opportunities. In: Omran, A., Schwarz-Herion, O. (eds) Sustaining our Environment for Better Future. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-7158-5_3
- Agriculture Sector Policy Framework (2012-2017). *Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Cooperatives and Rural Development, South Sudan.*
- Amin E. (2005). *Social Science Research, Conception, Methodology and Analysis*, Makerere University Press. Kampala.
- Bhattacharjee, A., (2012) '*Social Science Research. Principles, Methods, and Practices*' Tampa, Florida: USF Tampa Library Open Access Collections
- Cohen, K.L. & Ledford, (1994). *Conflicts management in Tanzania*, Dares salaam: East African Academy.
- Conference Report and Analysis (2016). *New Beginnings Way Forward for Transitional Justice in South Sudan*
- Cooper, R. & Schindler, P. (2007). *Business Research Methods*. New York: McGraw-Hill Publishers.
- Cresswell, J.W. & PlanoClark, V.L. (2011). *Designing and conducting mixed method research (2nd.ed.)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Creswell, J.W., (2004). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, mixed methods approach (2nded.)*. California: Sage Publications Inc.
- Dr. Radhika Kapur (2019). *Problems and Challenges in Rural Areas –Paper 14*
- Dr. Radhika Kapur (2019). *Rural Development Approaches and Strategies-Paper15*
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (2016 -2018, pg.5). *South Sudan Resilience Strategy*.
- Gholamhossein Hosseininia and Hadi Fallahi (2017) *Factors Affecting the Development of Rural Entrepreneurship: A Case Study on the Rural Areas of Manoojan County*
- Health Pooled Fund, South Sudan Study Report (2020). *Access to Health Care in South Sudan: A Qualitative Analysis of Health Pooled Fund Supported Counties*.
- Hinkelmann, K. & Witschel, H.F. (2003), *How to Choose Research Methodology? University of Applied Sciences North western Switzerland School of Business*.
- Infrastructure and Cities for Economic Development (2018). *South Sudan Infrastructure Sector Overview*.
- IOM South Sudan strategy (2019 -2022. Pg.13). *Return, Recovery & Resilience Strategy*.
- Jomehpour, M. (2017). *Identifying Strategic Priorities for the Sustainable Development of Rural Areas Based on Local Community Planning*. *Journal of Sustainable Rural Development*, 1(2), 161-170. <https://doi.org/10.29252/jsrd.01.02.161>.
- Kothari, C. (2004). *Research methodology: methods & techniques (2nd. Edition ed.)*. India... New age international publishers.
- Kothari, C.R. (2000). *Research Methodology, Methods and Techniques*. 2nd.Ed. International Publishers Ltd. Delh
- Leslie J. Bank & Tim GB Hart (2017) *how land reform and rural development can help reduce poverty in South Africa* <https://theconversation.com/how-land-reform-and-rural-development-can-help-reduce-poverty-in-south-africa-84146>
- Limpanitgul, T. (2009). *Methodological Considerations in a Quantitative Study Examining the Relationship Between Job Attitudes Citizenship Behaviors*. Soreze, France: Cardiff University
- Lin et al , (2019) *Differentiation of rural development driven by natural environment and urbanization: A case study of kashgar region, Northwest China*
- M Seraje (2007) *Livelihood Strategies and Their Implications for Rural-Urban Linkages: The Case of Wolenkomi Town and the Surrounding Rural Kebeles*
- Machuki, V.N. & Aosa, E., (2011) *The Influence External Environment on Performance of Publicly Quoted Companies in Kenya*, *Journal of Economic and Social Studies*,
- Mark Ginsburg et al (2017; Promoting community participation in improving education in South Sudan *African Educational Research Journal vol.5(4), pp.221-239, October 2017*.
- Mengistu, Diress (2010), "A Review of Selected Sector Policies of the Government of Southern Sudan to Identify Gaps in Food Security Policy." Report submitted to the
- Ministry of General Education and Instruction of South Sudan (2017-2022). *The General Education Strategic Plan*,
- Mugenda, O.M. & Mugenda, A.G. (2003), *Research Methods; Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches*, Acts Press, Nairobi, Kenya.
- Mugenda, M.O. & Mugenda, G. A. (2003). *Social Science Research: theory and Principals*. Nairobi: Applied Research and Training Services.
- Orodho, A.J. (2003). *Elements of Education Social Sciences Research Methods*. Maseno, Kenya: Masola Publisher.

- Oso, W.Y., & Onen, D. (2008). *Writing research proposal and report: A handbook for social research*, Patton, M.Q. (2001). *Qualitative evaluation and research methods* (3rd ed.). New bury park CA: Sage Publications.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P, &Thornhill, A. (2007) *Research Methods for Business Students.4 Ed. New Prentice Hall Small Business Economics, 23, 5,423-440*
- Saunders, M.,Lewis. Thornhill, A. (2009), *Research Methods for Business Students Fifth Edition*. Harlow, England: Prentice Hall Financial Times.
- Saunders, Me, Lewis, P. &Thornhill, A. (2012), *Research Methods for Business Students.6th ed. S l. Pearson Edition limited.*
- Save the Children (2019 -2021) *South Sudan Country Strategy Plan*.
- SekaranU., (2003), *Research Methods for Business. A Skill-Building Approach, Fourth Edition* Southern Illinois University of Carbondale
- Shamin et al (2022) *Classification of Factors Affecting the Development of Rural Area*
- South Sudan National Health Policy 2017 – 2026 (2016). *A community Anchored Health System for Sustainable Health Sector Development*.
- W E N DY S. AY R E S AND A L E X F. McCA LLA (1996). *Rural Development, Agriculture, and Food Security*<https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/fandd/1996/12/pdf/ayres.pdf>
- Wedawatta, G., Ingirige, B. &Amaratunga, D. (2011), case Study as a Research Strategy: *Investigating Extreme Weather Resilience of Construction SMEs in the UK United Kingdom: University of Safford, School of the Built Environment*
- Welman, C. Kruger, F. (2005), *Research methodology. Oxford University press*
- Wouterse et la. (2014)*How to build resilience to conflict: The role of food security*

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